

BENEFITS

- G-Brick-Eco panels are load bearing and thermally insulated building wall elements allowing for very **short construction times** both in renovation and new built.
- Suitable for **diffusion-closed construction systems**.
- Easy handling on site.
- **Fire resistance** for low- and midrise buildings.
- The **mechanical resistance is enhanced** by vertical ribs rigidly connecting both plywood surfaces
- When compared to competing products such as Cross Laminated Timber (CLT), G-Brick-Eco is much more **cost, energy and resource efficient**

Project innovation fact sheet

G-Brick-Eco

Biobased Structural Insulation Panel

APPLICATIONS

- Load-bearing walls and partitions
- Roofs and ceiling components
- Conventional buildings and tiny houses

NEXT STEPS

- **Upscaling** of the production facilities
- Optimising ribs adhesion process
- Automation of the production process

